

“THROUGH THE YEARS”: THE LIVED EXPERIENCE OF WEATHERED PSYCHIATRIC NURSES AT LEVEL III DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH HOSPITAL: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15318786>

ABSTRACT

This study, titled "Through the Years": The Lived Experience of Weathered Psychiatric Nurses at Level III Department of Health Hospital: Basis for an Intervention Enhancement Program, explored the lived experience of weathered psychiatric nurses who had been exposed to the unique demands of psychiatric wards. The research adopted a phenomenological approach, combined with Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), to examine the challenges, resilience, and coping mechanisms of nurses with extensive professional exposure in providing mental health care. Workplace violence, administrative challenges, and emotional stressors of nurses are issues that prevail but were often not discussed. This study aimed to point out the existence of these factors. The results identified 16 core themes with regard to professional stressors, emotional costs, and coping mechanisms. From these results, several intervention programs are recommended: Critical Incident Training and Support Programs, Emotional Resilience Workshops, Workplace Relationship Enhancement Programs, and Spiritual Counseling initiatives. These interventions were designed to address some critical issues, such as workplace violence, emotional burnout, interpersonal conflicts, and workload management. This study provided important insights for policymakers, hospital administrators, and mental health practitioners, with the goal toward the improvement of job satisfaction, mental health, and retention rates through improving the quality of psychiatric care.

Keywords: *psychiatric nurses, lived experience, resilience, workplace violence, intervention programs, phenomenological study*

INTRODUCTION

Weathered psychiatric nurses were skilled professionals who possessed a wealth of knowledge in the psychiatric nursing field. The researchers were particularly concerned about the need for skilled psychiatric nurses and the high rate of challenges within the psychiatric ward as mental health issues expanded and the need for specialized care increased. This critical situation compelled the researchers to embark on the lived experience of psychiatric nurses who had dedicated years to their demanding field.

Despite the challenges that psychiatric nurses faced, workplace violence had become an emerging global issue, more so in psychiatric settings. Compared to nurses who work in the public unit, mental health nurses face twice 20 times more physical violence compared to them; they also experience other forms of patient aggression more often than medical surgery nurses (Alshdefat & Baker, 2020). Apart from the foregoing, Zwane et al. (2020) revealed in the research findings that mental health nurses were confronted with a series of issues in their field such as assault, sexual harassment, especially against female nurses, psychological distress due to verbal mistreatment, discrimination, and stigma. On the same note, psychiatric nurses also faced administrative challenges that included overcrowding, inadequate supplies of medication, under-staffing, and inadequate infrastructure as well as equipment. The concerns highlighted a disturbing development in psychiatric nurses' workplace safety, underscoring a serious occupational hazard that required immediate attention to ensure the protection of mental health workers.

In the Philippines, Cruz et al. (2024) argued that the psychiatric setting had been less studied. The psychiatric field had not emphasized the working conditions of psychiatric nurses. Most studies conducted in the area focused on the individual with problems with their mental health rather than on the mental health practitioners working in psychiatric settings. This failure to prioritize denied psychiatric nurses the protection they deserved, even though they were exposed to enormous stressors when working with traumatized patients. Psychiatric nurses were frequently subjected to pressure in dealing with patients who had been through traumatic experiences or who were violent, which was a serious threat to their own well-being.

Addressing this gap was required to help the support needed by mental health professionals to handle their stressful job. The long-term psychiatric nurses' mental health was particularly crucial since they spent a lot of time dealing with difficult cases, like working with trauma patients whose behaviors were unstable and whose diseases were severe. Repeatedly dealing with these cases could end up causing severe mental health issues among psychiatric nurses.

Against this background of challenges, the current study aimed at enriching the existing knowledge on the lived experience of veteran psychiatric nurses in relation to their resilience, challenges, and coping mechanisms in their demanding career. Through a critical examination of these experiences, the study aimed at enlightening policymakers, healthcare administrators, and mental health support programs on the importance of establishing better and enhanced support systems for weathered psychiatric nurses. The results guided recommendations to enhance workplace practice, increase job satisfaction, promote mental well-being, and increase retention levels among psychiatric nurses. Most importantly, this study highlighted the need to acknowledge and respond to the unique needs of psychiatric nurses, which in turn benefited the nurses themselves and the quality of psychiatric care they delivered.

Research Questions

1. How do weathered psychiatric nurses describe their lived experience?
2. What themes emerge from the testimonies of weathered psychiatric nurses?
3. Based on the result of the study, what intervention program may propose?

METHODOLOGY

Population and Sampling

Within this qualitative study, the study used purposive sampling that ensured significance to the focus of study. This sampling approach was most appropriate because it allowed researchers to narrow down to specific individuals who had attributes and experience most related to the studied phenomenon. The researchers specifically chose head nurses who had worked at the same psychiatric hospital for decades, as their long working period provided rich qualitative data of the lived experience of weathered psychiatric nurses.

Purposive sampling, as Campbell et al. (2020) defined it, was interpreted differently. Some people viewed it as easy, but others believe it to be difficult. The primary objective was to define a sample that would be able to fit research. In all this, credibility, trust, and general rigour of the data enhanced and there would be better understanding of the phenomenon being studied.

Participant of the Study

This research included six (6) head nurses of any gender with over ten (10) years of experience at the Department of Health III Hospital. Participants were chosen for their long experience in the psychiatric setting, having been assigned to different pavilions in different classifications in the hospital. The population was limited to over ten years of experience as a nurse so that the participants had reached an acceptable level of expertise and strength in dealing with the intricacies of psychiatric care. This duration

allowed them to acquire a treasure trove of knowledge, skills, and strategies to cope with stress, with an in-depth understanding of their lived experience.

In this study, strict inclusion and exclusion criteria were developed to select the participant population of weathered psychiatric nurses within the Level III Department of Health Hospital. To be included in the participants, they had to be serving for more than (10) years in the psychiatric wards since such periods were taken to be critical for the deep insights into their lived experience in psychiatric nursing and building competence and resilience. Moreover, only head nurses whose careers included direct patient care in psychiatric settings across their practice were considered to ensure they were deeply involved in the core aspects of psychiatric nursing. Nurses with less than ten years of service were excluded to focus specifically on those with over a decade of experience, which is more aligned with the central objectives of the study.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers obtained permission from the university for their research paper prior to undertaking the process of writing to the Level III Department of Health Hospital. Once the proposal was accepted by the university, they wrote a formal letter to the Professional Education, Training, and Research Unit (PETRU) at Level III Department of Health Hospital. PETRU was the one to vet the research request, and the researchers were waiting for confirmation from PETRU prior to doing anything regarding the study. This guaranteed that all approvals were provided and the research conformed to the institution's ethical values and guidelines. PETRU gave the feedback, and after the researchers had made the required adjustments, the researchers waited for approval before going to the Ethics Review Committee (ERC).

Upon approval by PETRU, the study was submitted for consideration to the Ethics Review Committee to check if it met ethical standards. This served to ensure that the study was conducted under set ethics standards, thus protecting the welfare and rights of the participants before the conduct of interviews. Approved from ERC ensured proper execution in conducting research with respect to privacy and confidentiality besides the welfare of participants over the period of conducting the research. They, therefore, emailed the Data Protection Officer after getting clearance from TRC and ERC for collecting data. This was a move to ensure that all data protection regulations protocols were observed before conducting the interviews.

Once the clearance had been obtained, Nursing Education and Training Service (NETS), NETS scheduled the interviews, thereby ensuring that all protocols had been followed, and data collection could go on without complications. The participants for this research were identified and recruited with assistance from the Nursing Education and Training Services (NETS) at Level III Department of Health Hospital. Based on standards set, the team sent invitations to eligible psychiatric nurses with more than ten years of service. The signing of a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) by the chief nurse made it easy as these were ensured to follow the rules and regulations in administration of recruitment. Participants were sensitized on the aim and procedure of the research. This

collaborative approach aimed to assure a thorough and respectful recruitment process that, above all, had to be ethically sensitive while involving participants.

The interviews were conducted face to face at the Level III Department of Health Hospital. The research format was critical in setting rapport and ensuring open communication, which in turn ensures that participants are honest and comprehensive in their responses. In this study, there was no other applicable data collection method apart from the in-person interview, because it allowed the researcher to capture the nuances of participants' lived experience.

Instrument of the Study

Semi-structured interview questions were developed based on findings from a comprehensive literature review and relevant previous studies. The semi-structured interview included an aide-memoire containing rapport-building and debriefing questions. Even though debriefing questions addressed sensitive issues, they were asked at the end of the interview to give participants time to reflect on their experiences and thus ensure their well-being. This approach created an amiable interview environment and ensured all data were collected comprehensively.

To further test the reliability of the instrument, the questions were pretested on potential participants to ensure they were easy to understand. Pilot testing provided adequate feedback on clarity and ease of understanding. It validated the fact that the questions conveyed the intended concepts properly. The research advisor checked the instrument, and collaborative consultations by the researchers ensured that the instrument was valid for the intended use of the study. The step improved reliability and validity in data collection.

The research questions asked to the participants:

1. What motivates you to pursue psychiatric nursing?
2. Can you describe your journey into psychiatric nursing?
3. How has your role evolved over the years?
4. What factors influence you to stay in your role?
5. In what ways, working in a psychiatric setting influenced your daily life?
6. How your role in the psychiatric setting influenced your wellbeing?
7. Can you describe a particularly memorable experience that you encountered over the years of working as a psychiatric nurse?
8. Can you tell us about the most difficult situation you've encountered as a psychiatric nurse? How did you handle it?
9. How do you manage the workload of being a psychiatric nurse?
10. How do you usually cope with difficult situations in the workplace?

Validation of the Instrument

Three independent validators reviewed the research instrument and provided feedback regarding the clarity and appropriateness of the research instrument. The research instrument were tested to validate that they were properly framed to achieve the

goals of the study for the intended participants. The process of validation made the instrument more reliable and guaranteed that the questions accurately represented the desired constructs.

The criteria for validation were comprehensiveness, relevance, clarity, and consistency with the purpose of the study. The questions in the interview were designed to ensure proper capture and representation of the lived experience of weathered psychiatric nurses to generate high-quality data. Clarity was for ensuring that the questions were readable and pertinent to the research topic. Comprehensiveness was for the purpose of covering all dimensions relevant to the study, whereas consistency was for ensuring similarity of the questions to the study's purpose.

Data Analysis

The researcher used the method of thematic analysis in order to determine the lived experience of the weathered psychiatric nurses. Naeem et al. (2023) this is one such method where patterns or themes are identified and interpreted. It leads to new insights and understandings. The six steps of the Braun and Clarke thematic analysis approach are: (1) acquainting oneself with the data; (2) generating codes; (3) constructing themes; (4) reviewing themes; (5) designating and elucidating themes; and (6) providing examples (Mihas, 2022).

It enabled the researchers to identify the subtle and frequently intricate facets of the lived experience. The main ideas or themes that are consistent, unique, and significant in connection to the data set will be found and presented using thematic analysis. It will provide a thorough knowledge of the lived experience of the weathered psychiatric nurses. It will give an in-depth examination of each of them and the relevance of their lived experience.

Scope and Delimitation

The focus of the study was the lived experience of weathered psychiatric nurses in the Level III Department of Health Hospital. The Level III Department of Health Hospital was established under the Philippine Public Workers Act No. 3258. The hospital treated roughly 56,000 patients each year. It was recognized as a unique research training center and hospital by the Department of Health.

The researchers chose the Level III Department of Health Hospital for its extensive facilities, being prominent as the largest mental health institution, and large patient population, which provided an ideal setting to explore the lived experience of weathered psychiatric nurses. The participants were purposely selected and limited to the weathered psychiatric nurses who had more than (10) years of experience in the same psychiatric hospital. The researchers conducted the study over the course of a year from 2024-2025. Furthermore, six (6) weathered psychiatric nurses were selected to engage in semi structured interviews. Thematic analysis was utilized to uncover patterns and the themes of interview data. The research aimed solely to understand the lived experience of these weathered psychiatric nurses with extensive experience in the psychiatric setting.

RESULTS

CENTRAL THEMES	SUB-THEMES	DESCRIPTION	CODES
1. Motivation to Pursue Psychiatric Nursing	1.1 Interest in Psychology	Participants were passionate about psychology.	Interest, Career Aspiration, Career Shift
	1.2 Family Influence	Family influenced participants through support, motivation and exposure to psychiatry.	Financial Responsibilities, Family Motivation, Early Exposure
2. Journey into Psychiatric Nursing	2.1 Challenges in Entering the Field	Participants found psychiatric nursing challenging, requiring patience and training.	Patient Handling, Emotional Demands, Training Challenges
	2.2 Personal and Professional Growth	Participants found fulfillment and enjoyment in their nursing roles.	Personal Growth and Fulfillment, Helping Others, Ongoing Fulfillment
	2.3 Family Influence on Career Decisions	Participants were influenced by family and opportunities in their nursing journey.	Parental Encouragement, Parental Influence, External opportunity
3. Evolution of Role Over the Years	3.1 Career Progression	Participants expanded roles, advanced careers and developed clinical intuition.	Expanding Responsibilities, Career Progression, Developing Clinical Intuition
	3.2 Developing Clinical Judgment	Awareness of patient signs.	Clinical Eye
	3.3 Mentorship and Support	Support from mentors played a vital role in their professional development.	Guidance
4. Factors Influencing Retention	4.1 Job Security and Benefits	Government hospital benefits and salary were strong factors in nurses' decision to stay.	Salary, Benefits, Stable Employment
	4.2 Commitment to Patients	Many nurses stayed because of their dedication to patient care and the fulfillment they gained from seeing patients improve.	Patient Care, Passion Commitment, Patient Connection
	4.3 Family as Motivator	Participants expressed how their responsibilities and commitment to their loved ones served a key motivator.	Family Responsibility, Family-Driven Commitment

5. Influence on Daily Life	5.1 Interpersonal Skills	Working in psychiatry improved their ability to communicate and understand others.	Improved Patience, Better Communication
	5.2 Emotional Resilience	Participants manage their emotions effectively	Managing Stress, Handling Emotions.
6. Workload Management Strategies	6.1 Time Management and Organization	Participants emphasized organizing tasks systematically and managing time effectively.	Prioritizing Tasks, Time Management, Organized
	6.2 Teamwork and Task Delegation	Participants relied on teamwork to manage workload.	Collaboration, Endorsement, Team Support
7. Memorable and Most Difficult Situations	7.1 Unforgettable Experiences	Participants shared moments that left a lasting impression.	Work Bonding, Positive Relationship, Building Trust, Memorable Experience
	7.2 Most Challenging Situations	Participants shared handling challenging patients.	Critical Incidents, Patient Aggression, Threats Received, Emotional Burden, High-Risk Patients
8. Coping Mechanisms	8.1 Emotional Regulation	Participants employed various strategies to manage stress.	Calm Assessment, Patience and Empathy, Positive Mindset
	8.2 Work-Life Balance	Participants balanced life with hobbies, loved ones, and rest.	Healthy Routine, Engaging in Hobbies, Selfcare, Faith

Thematic Table 1. *The Lived Experience of Weathered Psychiatric Nurses*

DISCUSSION

1. Motivation to Pursue Psychiatric Nursing is the main theme, explaining why nurses enter this specialty area. The extracts demonstrated that nurses were motivated based on two sub-themes: 1.1 Interest in Psychology and 1.2 Family Influence. Participants began to be highly interested in psychology during school and, for that reason, ended up studying psychiatric nursing. Other motivations were due to family factors: financial need, encouragement, or personal experience of the psychiatric field, for example, having been raised in a hospital setting.

Sub-Theme 1.1: Interest in Psychology

P4: "Paborito ko ang subject na Psychology... Even before, two courses kasi ako. Doon sa unang course ko, maganda rin yung grades ko sa psychology... Tapos, nung nag-nursing ako, maganda rin yung grades ko sa psychology."

P3: "Dati kasi nung nag-aaral pa lang ako, yung subject na psychology is gusto ko siya"

gawin specialty...”

P6: “I failed the bar exam... I like the psychiatric set up so much.”

The sub-theme Interest in Psychology was seen in the statements of P4, P3, and P6. In the statements, the participants mentioned their passion for understanding human behavior and mental health. P4 stated that psychology was his favorite subject; therefore, he was naturally drawn to the field. P3 stated that initially, they wanted to specialize in psychology, so their interest in the subject had been a reason for them to pursue their career in this field. P6 pointed out that it was immediately after failing the bar exam, actually, when they had fallen in love with psychiatric nursing as a field. The enthusiasm for psychology led them to a whole new path in the mental health sphere altogether.

Mlambo et al. (2021) study underscored the issue of lifelong learning in nursing careers, especially in those nurses who were motivated by what they were learning, such as psychology. Learning through patients while under mentorship refined psych skills, mainly in psychiatric set-ups. This perfectly resonated with the study since participants, like P3 and P6, shared how they were motivated to turn to psychiatric nursing due to their interest in psychology. Interest drove them to learn more, contributing both to personal growth and professional competence in this special field.

Sub-Theme 1.2: Family Influence

P2: “First ay sa family ko. Meron financial aspect. Naipo provide ko yung mga needs nila.”

P5: “Family. Ayun yung first... Family talaga ang nag motivate saakin na i-pursue ang psychiatric nursing.”

P4: “Batang mental kasi ako. My mom was a psychologist here. So playground ko itong mental na maliit pa ako. Isa yon sa nag-motivate saakin...”

The sub-theme Family Influence showed that the participants' families had been the most influential factor in their choice of being psychiatric nurses. P2 mentioned that the financial support for his family had been a major reason for choosing this career. P5 also explained that the support of their family had been their driving force. In contrast, P4 had lived most of their childhood in a psychiatric hospital since their mother had been working there as a psychologist, which had automatically instilled in them interest in the field at an early age.

A research conducted by Pisker (2022) that examined occupational choices among various cultures concluded that family expectations and customs had strongly influenced people toward occupational choices such as nursing, thereby affirming that family pressures and values influence career choices.

The overall theme **2. Journey into Psychiatric Nursing** demonstrated the way in which the participants learned to deal with various challenges and development upon entry into the profession. While some encountered 2.1 Difficulties in Entering the Profession, others had to deal with 2.2 Family Influence on Career Decisions. In spite of

these issues, they do have 2.3 Personal and Professional Development, learning to cope with patients and become resilient over time.

Sub-Theme 2.1: Challenges in Entering the Field

P1: “Yung years of experience ko is very challenging... lahat acute chronic work... sobrang hindi rin biro mag-handle ng psychiatric patients.”

P5: “Hindi siya madali... Mahirap siya... lalo na kapag pakikitungo a mga pasyente... nangangailangan ng sobrang pasensya at pang unawa.”

P4: “This is my first job mahirap din yung naging buhay namin... kasi lahat ng trainings kailangan pagdaan mo, lahat ng areas kailangan ikutan mo.”

The sub-theme Challenges in Entering the Field revealed that the participants had many challenges when they initially began their practice as psychiatric nurses. P1 indicated that it was tough to take care of both acute and chronic psychiatric patients, stating that it was challenging and hard. P5 stated that psychiatric patients required a lot of patience and tolerance. Similarly, P4 stated that as a fresh nurse, more training was also conducted, and the nurse routine in fields of work brings in the challenge during adaptation to psychiatric nursing care.

Sub-theme 2.1 Challenges in Entering the Field revealed that psychiatric nurses encountered severe challenges upon entering the field. Mangano et. al (2020) study corroborated this by revealing that psychiatric nurses who were new entrants had difficulties proving themselves competent in numerous aspects, such as knowledge, skills, and managing patients. This concurred with the experience of P1 in handling both chronic and acute psychiatric patients, which it portrayed as demanding and difficult.

Similarly, the study Cranage and Foster (2022) validated the challenges of resource shortages, emotional exhaustion, and psychiatric nursing stigma. This validated P5's claim of needing extreme patience and empathy while dealing with psychiatric patients. This also echoed with P4's account of experiencing rigorous training and rotations in other departments prior to adjusting to the psychiatric nursing environment.

Sub-Theme 2.2: Personal and Professional Growth

P3: “Naghintay ako ng mga 2 years before ma-hired. Ganon katagal. Nag-start ako sa nursing attendant pa lang and now ay, head nurse na ako.”

P5: “...nahanap ko ang fulfillment sa trabaho ko, lalo na’t alam kong nakakatulong ako sa mga tao na dumadaan sa mahihirap na pagsubok...sa paglipas ng panahon, nakita ko kung paano ako lumago bilang tao at nurse, natutong mag-develop ng compassion at resilience.”

P4: “It was also a fulfilling experience for me... I’ve been a nurse 2 for 7 years. And it’s still a good experience for me. I still welcome ang pagpasok araw-araw. Every day is a new day.”

The sub-theme Personal and Professional Growth indicates that the participants

both professionally developed and grew as individuals as psychiatric nurses. In this connection, P3 mentioned they were initially appointed as a nursing attendant and subsequently after two years worked as a head nurse, which is evidence of professional development. P5 indicated that they were content in their work overtime since they had acquired sympathy and resilience as they helped patients navigate their challenging circumstances. P4 also elaborated their extensive career as a psychiatric nurse as rewarding, suggesting that they still enjoyed purpose in their work and looked forward to reporting to work daily.

Javanmardnejad et al. (2021) observed that job satisfaction had a significant influence on a nurse's performance, commitment, and well-being. This was echoed by P5, who was content in her job as she grew sympathy and strength in educating patients. More importantly, it was found from the research that quality of working life played an important role in determining a nurse's happiness and job satisfaction because P4 expressed that their lengthy career as a psychiatric nurse was satisfying and significant. Additionally, aspects like career development, peer relationships, and professional growth enhanced nurses' growth in general. This was demonstrated in P3 who was able to advance from a nursing attendant to a head nurse within two years, thus demonstrating professional growth. In general, these results showed that psychiatric nurses' growth both personally and professionally was critical in ensuring job satisfaction and the provision of quality patient care.

Sub-Theme 2.3: Family Influence on Career Decisions

P2: "Ang mother ko, in-encourage ako mag-nursing. And then, yung pinsan ko kasi is dito na rin siya nagtatrabaho as a psych nurse."

P6: "Ang plano ko talaga noon ay magpatuloy sa pagkuha ng law career... pero nang hindi ako pumasa sa bar exam, pinush ako ng nanay ko na maghanap ng ibang option."

The subtheme Family influence on Career Decision reflected a very high significant role that was played by families in psychiatric nurse career choice, where it emerges that for P2 that motivated them into this career choice with their mother convincing them to nurse, having also a cousin, which also confirmed the idea with him already nursing. Similarly, P6 wanted to be a lawyer, but when they failed the bar exam, their mother pushed them to find another career path, which is how they became a nurse.

Maor and Cojocaru (2018) reported that family influence had a stronger impact on becoming psychiatric nurses, and Nawabi and Javed (2019) stated that parental perception had its share in professional decision-making. P2 was motivated by both his mother and cousin, and P6 had been guided through their mother's encouragement. The findings supported the statement that psychiatric nurses were molded in terms of family support that also helped them stay committed and engaged with the profession.

The central theme was **3. Evolution of Role Over the Years**. It is how psychiatric nurses grew and evolved in their profession. The 3.1 Career Progression of psychiatric nurses was reflected in how they advanced through their roles to gain more responsibilities over the years. 3.2 Developing Clinical Judgment emphasized experience

that builds one's ability in decision-making and management of a patient. 3.3 Mentorship and Support revealed the way family and colleagues influenced their career choices and professional growth.

Sub-Theme 3.1: Career Progression

P1: “sobrang laki ng pagbabago ng role ko... hindi lang sa mga trainings kundi pati na rin sa mga hands-on experiences ko during my residency at rotations. Yung mga experiences na yun... tumulong sa akin para magkaroon ng mas malawak na pananaw at mga skills na kailangan ko para maging effective sa trabaho.”

P3: “Nagsimula ako bilang Nursing Assistant (NA) muna. Tapos, after two and a half years, pinag-apply na ako as Nurse 1.”

P5: “isa sa mga napansin kong mahalagang pagbabago sa aking tungkulin ay pagiging mas persistent na magpatuloy at gawin ang best ko despite the challenges... Ang importante ay magpatuloy ka at laging magbigay ng best effort mo, kahit mahirap.”

The sub-theme Career Progression showed the evolution of psychiatric nurses in their jobs. P1 states that training and experiences made during residency helped them master their required skills for effective work. P3 was trained initially as a Nursing Assistant, and after gathering experience in the job, he or she was influenced to apply for the higher position. P5 puts persistence and giving one's best effort despite the odds during the course as qualities that are necessary for career growth, demonstrating that one needs to continually learn and persevere.

Arianta and Goller (2024) maintain that resilience and networks contributed to the completion of training and professional career advancement. This is in line with P1, as they learned through residency and practicing. Exec (2023) maintained that Continuous Learning and Professional Development is essential. In this case, P3 changed job from being a Nursing Assistant to another higher role based on training and cumulative experience. On the other hand, study on weathered psychiatric nurses revealed that long-term practice led to the achievement of resilience and adaptability, which consistent with P5 as a belief that persistence and consistent effort are required for career growth. These connections reinforced that career growth in psychiatric nursing is dynamic and is developed by training, experience, and hard work.

Sub-Theme 3.2: Developing Clinical Judgment

P2: “Habang tumatagal, natututo kami kung paano maging alerto sa mga signs na nagpapakita na malapit na mag-react ang pasyente... kaya nagkaroon kami ng ‘clinical eye’ para malaman kung ano ang kailangan nila. “

P6: “yung mga behavior ng pasyente, minsan kapag nakita ko sa mga tao sa labas masasabi ko sa sarili ko, “oy, parang pasyente ka na”... Natutunan ko na i-identify yung mga anong klaseng behavior.”

The sub-theme Developing Clinical Judgment showed how psychiatric nurses developed their judgment skills when seeing patients over time. P2 said that over time,

one becomes more vigilant of the cues that might reflect a patient's potential response; hence, interventions can be preemptively prepared. For instance, P6 averred that exposure to psychiatric areas enabled them to identify specific behaviors outside the hospital among people they would otherwise not engage. Many were able to identify almost the same patterns shown by patients. This revealed how their eye in patient care has been enhanced through repeated exposure and active practice within the psychiatric ward. Such a skill is crucial in maintaining patient safety as well as appropriate care.

According to Burdeu et al. (2020) acute care nurses relied on clinical cues to know when a patient's condition has changed, a skill they acquire through repeated exposure and experience. The study explained the need for understanding the scope of assessment skills that nurses deploy, including detecting deterioration, resonating with the experiences of P2 and P6 in terms of developing a "clinical eye" over time. The conclusions were that incessant practice on the psychiatric ward made nurses efficient in assessing and caring for the patients.

Sub-Theme 3.3: Mentorship and Support

P4: "May mga mentors na nag-guide sakin... pati na rin yung mga naging preceptors ko, ay maayos na nakasama. Whatever I've achieved today, I owe it to the mentors and preceptors I've met along the way."

The sub-theme Mentorship and Support arose because the participants underlined that they valued mentorship as a key factor in their working life as psychiatric nurses. P4 indicated that they had been lucky to have competent mentors and preceptors who had mentored them, influencing their career development. They were convinced that they had achieved their success through the support and expert knowledge inherited from the mentors.

This was supported by Glanzer (2022), who added that mentorship was a well-established practice to engage, retain, and connect people to the nursing career, affirming that formal mentorship programs were crucial for professional success. The results reinforced the notion that formal mentorship programs were considered essential support, fostering a setting in which nurses grow in careers and are successful. During the interview, P4 displayed a sense of gratitude and appreciation when discussing their mentors and preceptors. The facial expression softened and the tone became reflective.

The main theme **4. Factors Influencing Retention** existed because participants shared the reasons why they stayed in their jobs as psychiatric nurses. 4.1 Job Security and Benefits gave them financial stability and assurance, making them feel secure in their profession. Their 4.2 Commitment to Patients motivated them to continue despite challenges, as they found meaning in caring for those in need. Lastly, 4.3 Family Support played a critical role as, feeling fulfilled in their work, they wanted to stay in that position.

Sub-Theme 4.1: Job Security and Benefits

P1: "Yung main reason to stay syempre unang-una is yung job... dahil alam naman natin

na mahirap din maghanap ng trabaho... Yung salary.... kahit paano naman is maganda na rin naman yung salary ng mga nurses sa government. And then... yung pinaka-benefits namin..."

P2: "Okay naman yung mga compensation na naibibigay.... nasa government hospital ka kaya maraming mga benefits."

The sub-theme Job Security and Benefits was mentioned because the participants highlighted the way financial stability and employment security decided their stay as psychiatric nurses. P1 said that the pay in government hospitals was okay, and the benefits were an important reason to stick around. P2 further added that the remuneration and benefits offered in the government hospitals were just fine. In addition, P1 mentioned that making the job search was stressful. Therefore, stable employment had been one major factor in their staying in their profession.

This was in line with Duru and Hammoud (2022) who established that the key retention drivers for nurses included competitive compensation and benefits, as it helped to provide the job security and financial stability that fostered a retention force in staying nurses at their workplace. Further results that support findings in participants were about the realization that the availability of benefits in salary, health coverage, and job security mainly served to act as motivation that led to more nurses remaining within the workplace settings.

Sub-Theme 4.2: Commitment to Patients

P2: "there's the need to care for patients, as they also deserve proper attention."

P3: "Kasi kapag mahal mo yung ginagawa mo... hindi mo sya basta basta tatalikuran..."

P4: "rewarding feeling na makita ang improvement ng mga pasyente, lalo na sa psychiatric nursing...if you try to communicate with your patients, if you're sincere enough to learn who they are, understand who they are..."

The sub-theme Commitment to Patients was seen because the interviewees described their commitment to providing care to psychiatric patients. P2 reported staying within the profession since there was a need to take care of patients, suggesting that patients required proper attention. A deep love for the work made it hard for P3 to leave; in this case, emotional commitment by the role forced them to stay. P4 also explained the satisfaction that comes with seeing patients improve, especially when they try to communicate genuinely and listen to their patients, which shows how dedicated they are to the care of their patients.

This aligns with Baljoon et al. (2018) nurses' motivation and the standard of care they deliver are closely correlated with their passion for their work. Similarly, resonated with Setoodeh et al. (2025) who stated that compassion competence was essential for nurses to build a good therapeutic relationship and deliver care that supported patient recovery. P3 stated that love for the job made it difficult to leave, thus showing emotional attachment to the job, a point that was also underscored, pointing out that such emotional attachment was crucial in ensuring quality care for patients. Additionally, P4 described

the rewarding feeling of seeing patient improvement, particularly when they communicated sincerely and understood their patients. It underscored that understanding and addressing patients' needs through compassionate care was fundamental to psychiatric nursing practice.

Throughout the interview, the participants exhibited evident emotional commitment through their physical cues. P2 addressed the interviewer with a confident tone and steady eye contact. P3 exhibited a warm smile, smiled on occasion, and employed hand movements. P4 leaned forward slightly with a relaxed facial expression, evident emotional commitment when referring to patient improvement.

Sub-Theme 4.3: Family Support

P2: "main reason is sa family..."

P5: "Mas motivated ako dahil sa family talaga.... mas nagbigay sa akin ng drive at motivation yung responsibility ko sa kanila."

P6: "To stay here because of my wife."

The sub-theme Family Support was realized, as participants discussed how their families motivated them to stay in the jobs. P2 indicated that the primary reason for staying in the job was family, highlighting how family relationships influence their choice. P5 stated that the family gives one the drive and motivation to stay at work; this was, however, marked by a feeling of responsibility. P6 attributed his staying because of his commitment to his wife, which exemplifies how personal relationships were the center of professional commitment.

Gagnano et al. (2020) study that work-life balance between family and work is a major indicator of job satisfaction and staying intentions among nurses. The authors suggested that support from the family made nurses more willing to continue with their careers, even when there were problems at work. This was consistent with Sub-Theme 4.3: Family Support, wherein participants stated that their family inspired them to remain in their jobs.

The central theme **5. Influence on Daily Life** revealed itself as the participants explained how work affected their personal and emotional well-being. Sub-Theme 5.1: Interpersonal Skills found its space as participants said working with psychiatric patients had improved their communication skills and ability to understand other people better. Sub-Theme 5.2: Emotional Resilience, where they described learning to manage stress and remain calm under difficult situations, was also shown.

Sub-Theme 5.1: Interpersonal Skills

P1: "as a psychiatric nurse... meron na kami knowledge about dealing with people. Na-apply naman din namin siya sa everyday, kahit sa personal life.. very helpful."

P2: "yung pagkakaroon ng mas malawak na kaisipan, tsaka yung patience, kailangan

intindihan mo sila. So, dapat mahaba din ng pasensya ng isang psychiatric nurse. Yung how you communicate...Yung therapeutic na pakikipag-usap ”

P4: “you tend to be more understanding of the situation ng mga tao... Hindi mo lang siya titignan dahil galit siya, you tend to ask na anong pinagdaanan niya at umabot siya sa sitwasyon na yon... kung may empathy 1.0 ka nun ngayon 2.0 ka na.”

The sub-theme Interpersonal Skills existed because psychiatric nurses developed good communication and understanding in their work, which they applied in their everyday life. P1 said that knowledge of how to deal with people helped them personally and professionally. P2 mentioned patience and therapeutic communication as key to understanding the patients. P4 pointed out that over time, empathy grew and one could see beyond a person's anger and understand their experiences better. These answers indicate that work in psychiatric nursing develops nurses' empathy with other people.

The study by Ahmed and Said (2023) highlighted how experienced psychiatric nurses developed strong interpersonal skills over time, which played a crucial role in patient care. Their findings showed that empathy, refined communication skills, and strong support systems were essential for maintaining effective therapeutic relationships with patients. This aligned with Sub-Theme 5.1: Interpersonal Skills, as nurses improved their ability to communicate, applied patience and understanding in interactions, and used empathy to connect with patients beyond their immediate behaviors. These insights reinforced that psychiatric nursing required both technical knowledge and interpersonal competence to provide high-quality patient-centered care.

Sub-Theme 5.2: Emotional Resilience

P3: “ araw araw may bagong matututunan mula sa mga pasyente. Tinutulungan natin sila... may mga bagay din silang itinuro sa atin. Nakakatulong din sa pagdeal sa mga challenges sa life.”

P5: “ yung mga challenges na kinakaharap ko, natutunan ko kung paano mag- manage ng emotions at mag adjust sa mga situations... mas madali i-handle.”

The sub-theme Emotional Resilience existed because psychiatric nurses learned to manage their emotions and adapt themselves to difficult situations. According to P3, new lessons were learned every day from the patients that helped them handle life challenges. P5 said that facing challenges in their work taught them how to control their emotions and adapt themselves to different situations more conveniently. These experiences showed psychiatric nursing strengthened the ability to stay emotionally strong and well-equipped to cope with stress situations.

Alonazi et al. (2023) supported this by stating that psychiatric nurses who had higher psychological resilience levels felt more job satisfaction and were capable of managing work-related stress well. This highlighted how emotional resilience helped psychiatric nurses to maintain their well-being as they delivered good quality care for patients.

The central theme **6. Workload Management Strategies** depicted how psychiatric nurses were able to effectively manage their daily tasks. Under 6.1 Time Management and Organization, the nurses revealed how they had planned their time and managed their tasks in such a way that they could avoid stress and stay productive. In 6.2 Teamwork and Task Delegation, they discussed how they worked as a team and delegated tasks to other colleagues to share the workload.

Sub-Theme 6.1: Time Management and Organization

P1: "I handled it in a systematic way for me... mas i-prioritize ang time, saka yung pinaka workload para matapos mo yung task mo."

P3: "Ako kasi pag trabaho, trabaho talaga...time management lang din... pag sobrang busy ka na meron kang mas kailangan unahin."

P4: "it's just being organized... at kung alam mo na yung routine mo, hindi ka na mahihirapan mag-organize... Identifying your priorities..."

The sub-theme Time Management and Organization, according to P1, planned tasks systematically by giving priority on time and work to do everything on schedule. P3 said that in their case, they focused on work and depended on time management on what needs to be done first, especially when things get busy. P4: "*kung alam mo na yung routine mo, hindi ka na mahihirapan mag-organize*".

The results of Filomeno et al. (2023) supported Sub-Theme 6.1: Time Management and Organization, where psychiatric nurses had managed their workload by planning and prioritizing appropriately. P1 managed tasks in a systematic manner by focusing on time and workload, ensuring that everything was done on time, which reflected the study's emphasis on goal-setting and organization. P3 stated that time management helped them determine which tasks to prioritize, especially during busy periods, supporting the study's conclusion that proper scheduling enhanced productivity. Additionally, P4 emphasized that familiarity with routines made organizing tasks easier, reinforcing the study's finding that structured work routines improved efficiency and reduced stress in psychiatric nursing.

Sub-Theme 6.2: Teamwork and Task Delegation

P1: "ako naman as a senior nurse, I have my other colleagues... So, I can handle it by giving them tasks."

P2: "more on sa paperwork, siyempre, pag hindi natatapos... May endorsement time naman."

P6: "Sa team namin, tulungan kami... May suporta kaya manageable..."

The sub-theme Teamwork and Task Delegation P1 stated that as a senior nurse, they managed responsibilities by delegating tasks to others. P2 stated that whenever paperwork was incomplete, they passed it onto the next shift, ensuring that tasks were

being done. P6 stated that their team collaborated with each other, which eased workload. This indicates teamwork and task delegation for effective use of duties.

Moradi et al. (2024) study mentioned the significance of teamwork and task delegation in performing nursing responsibilities and ensuring patient safety. This aligned with Sub-Theme 6.2: Teamwork and Task Delegation, as the findings showed that team collaboration facilitated nurses to effectively manage their workload. The study revealed that the delegation of duties to team members reduced stress, improved workflow, and the quality of care provided to patients. Similarly, the psychiatric nurses in the study maintained their workload by assigning tasks, authorizing pending tasks, and supporting each other, confirming the essence of teamwork in the maintenance of effectiveness and healthiness in healthcare institutions.

Theme 7. **Memorable and Most Difficult Situations** described the situations of psychiatric nurses in terms of meaningful situations. In 7.1 Unforgettable Experiences, the nurses told stories that were unforgettable to them, like observing a patient getting better or developing significant relationships with their patients. In 7.2 Most Difficult Situations, the nurses described their struggles with handling aggressive patients, handling emotional hurt, and processing too much at once. These experiences shaped their resilience and professional growth, showing how both positive and difficult moments influenced their journey as psychiatric nurses.

Sub-Theme 7.1: Unforgettable Experiences

P1: "We have here yearly na activities like Christmas party or class or pavilion na magmeet kami ng mga employee para makapag-banding, para makapag-enjoy, and then celebrate."

P3: "... lahat sila sinasabi na namimiss nila ako.. parang satisfied sa aking pakikisama."

P2: "Makukulit sila pero nakukuha mo rin kung paano sila sayuin, amuhin... yung paano makuha yung trust nila... marami silang energy, so dapat magbibigyan mo sila ng pansin."

P4: "Yung survivor ng Yolanda.. I remember the sincerity of his story and we were able to help... sincere ang pagkakakwento niya... Ang remarkable ng story... Hindi ko malimutan..."

The sub-theme Unforgettable Experiences highlighted the meaningful and memorable moments psychiatric nurses had during their work. P1 shared how annual activities like Christmas parties and gatherings helped strengthen bonds among employees and bring joy to their workplace. P3 expressed appreciation for the positive relationships built with patients, as they felt valued and missed by those they cared for. P2 and P4 remembered some special moments, like when they gained the trust of patients and heard a survivor's heartwarming story, which really made an impact on them. These experiences revealed how joyful occasions and close relationships with patients influenced their progression as psychiatric nurses.

Girard et al. (2021) a therapeutic nurse-patient relationship played a crucial part in quality care, which in turn closely aligned with P2 and P4's experience of gaining trust of

patients and listening to authentic stories. Consequently, the nurses' work became more meaningful and fulfilling by developing strong relationships with patients. In the same vein, Radu (2023) cited that a good work culture was to be blamed for a motivated workforce, exemplifying how activities like annual celebrations maintained the nurses united and content with their job, as seen in the case of P1 and P3. Of importance, both patient relationships and work relationships contributed to the iconic experiences of psychiatric nurses.

Throughout the interview, P4 had a softer face and mumbled in a low tone in retelling the story. P4 would stop every now and then, the eyes almost brimming up, as if reliving the scene. P4 body leaned forward slightly, and the hands clamped harder together, indicating intense emotional involvement. The eyes darted down sometimes, and the breathing slowed down, showing the gravity of the memory.

Sub-Theme 7.2: Most Challenging Situations

P1: “meron akong isang patient na nag-escape and then nag-attempt na mag- suicide... the most difficult for me is solo ka sa duty and then... an incident happens... you are on your own so you must decide on prioritization...”

P3: “Nahila na rin pala one-time yung buhok ko ng pasyente... Disturbed yun”

P4: “Nakatanggap na ako ng death threat sa pasyente...”

P5: “most difficult lang yung pagkakaroon ka na incident like death... mabigat siya ng ilang araw... Para bang kailangan mo ng oras para makapag process.”

P6: “meron akong takas na dalawang pasyente... may kaso na murder and theft. It's part of our job. Incident, accident, issue... mga difficult patient...”

The sub-theme Most Challenging Situations emphasized the complicated and risky experience psychiatric nurses undertook in clinical practice. P1 and P6 remembered the incidence of a patient trying to escape, whereby some had been involved in crime, making things more dangerous. P3 and P4 indicated experiences of encountering physical violence and verbal abuse by distressed patients, showing nurses' exposure while handling patient care. P5 explained the psychological burden of patient deaths, emphasizing the lasting impact these accidents had on their well-being.

Jafar and Nazir (2023) pointed out that the psychiatric nurses were highly burnt out due to understaffing, heavy workload, and patient aggression, making it one of the hardest nursing jobs. The fact that P1 was the sole nurse on duty when there was a critical incident is an indicator of the understaffing pressures. In the same vein, P3 and P4 were also exposed to violence, which served to further establish the likelihood of workplace violence within psychiatric units. P6 experienced challenges in handling high-risk patients who tried to escape or expressed overt threats, which further entrenched the dangers nurses had to endure. These results stressed the need for improved support mechanisms, increased security measures, and effective coping mechanisms to aid

psychiatric nurses in combating such issues at the cost of their psychological well-being.

The Central theme **8. Coping Mechanisms** showed how psychiatric nurses coped with stress and remained healthy in the face of the demanding job. 8.1 Emotional Regulation enabled them to remain calm when times were challenging by controlling their emotions and coping with harsh environments. 8.2 Work-Life Balance enabled them to recharge by engaging in personal activities, which kept them physically and mentally healthy and able to still care for their patients effectively.

Throughout the interview, the participants had different levels of tension as they narrated their worst experiences. P1 had a stiff posture, with hands crossed and eyebrows slightly knitted, expressing the burden of having to make life-and-death decisions all by themselves. P3 gently touched the hair when speaking. P5 took a deep sigh and hesitated before answering, reflecting the emotional burden of handling patient fatalities. P4 was at ease, answered softly and calmly and P6 seemed nonchalant, leaned back slightly, and answered in an even voice, viewing the difficulties as an ordinary aspect of work.

Sub-Theme 8.1: Emotional Regulation

P1: "maging relax lang muna... Then, assess mo muna kung anong dapat mangyari... saka ako mag-aact na naayon po aking mind... I'll make sure naman na napag-isip ako."

P3: "kailangan lang talaga yung mahaba... ang pasensya natin... may empathy..."

P4: "mag-focus na lang sa positibo at gawin ang trabaho na maayos.. Nasa mindset na lang talaga yon."

The participants kept themselves relaxed and reflective before working. P1 stated, *"maging relax lang muna... Then, evaluate mo muna kung anong dapat mangyari... saka ako mag-aact na naayon po aking mind... I'll ensure naman na napag-isip ako."* P3 stated that patience and understanding towards the issue one has to face is required. P4 stated that proper work and good mind is required, showing the advantage of emotional control for workers at the workplace.

Kraiss et al. (2020) also highlighted the importance of emotion regulation techniques in enhancing mental well-being, particularly in a stressful environment. Likewise, the participants regulated their emotions by being calm and introspective prior to decision-making (P1), exercising patience and empathy (P3), and having a positive attitude while doing their job (P4). These techniques substantiated the point that effective emotional regulation minimized psychological distress and maximized job performance. By executing these strategies, the participants demonstrated how emotional regulation allowed them to be professionally and well resilient.

Sub-Theme 8.2: Work-Life Balance

P1: "Syempre , we do exercise. And then, yung everyday routine makes me healthy. I will make sure na.. I eat three times a day."

P6: "Ginagawa ko ay magkaroon ng daily exercise... Normally kasi dito ay puro may relihiyon at paniniwala sa Diyos.... Manampalataya...kung atheist ka, kawawa ka."

P2: "pwede isulat ang nararamdaman mo, or you go to, mag aliw-aliw, or mag-bakasyon..."

P4: " ang ginagawa ko lang siguro, just to de-stress myself is.. To maintain my well-being, is to do the things that I love to do... If you don't have self-care, baka matulad ka sa pasyente."

The participants maintain work-life balance by having healthy habits and engaging in self-care. P1 and P6 considered exercise to be very important. P2 cited activities such as writing, traveling, and fun to help in the reduction of stress. P4 emphasized self-care and indicated that failure to do so might result in burnout. The children, P5 and P6, coped with stress by having personal space, avoiding work chats, and finding comfort in faith, suggesting that work-life balance helped them maintain their mental and emotional well-being.

Work-life balance meant dedicating time to work but also maintaining personal well-being (Gawande, 2024). This was clear in the experiences of psychiatric nurses, as P1 and P6 focused on exercise, whereas P2 pursued activities such as writing and travel to cope with stress. Further, P4 stressed self-care as a measure against burnout, and P5 balanced it by setting limits, including not taking work conversations during free time. These activities illustrated how maintaining self-care and personal space aided the participants in addressing work demands without compromising their well-being.

Conclusions

1. The day-to-day reality of weathered psychiatric nurses was one of subtle complexity involving a mature tension between professional gratification and chronic struggle. Despite resilience and goal-focused in rendering psychiatric services, they were exposed to high levels of emotional, psychological, and physical strain. Their ability to manage these pressures was largely a function of personal coping mechanisms, interagency communication, and commitment to patients. But the study also found very important issues regarding workplace support, institutions policy measures, and mental health care programs that would have maintained their welfare and professional viability in a much better way. Resolving these issues through systematized interventions and policy corrective actions was significant to enable psychiatric nurses to get the proper care to keep rendering high-quality service while protecting their own welfare and health.
2. According to the findings of the study, a program of intervention was suggested for improving the well-being of psychiatric nurses. The program aimed to improve mental health support systems, develop systematic stress management training, offer continuous professional development, and enhance workplace policies to mitigate staff shortages and occupational risks. Intervention strategies proposed

included peer support programs, access to counseling services, formal debriefing, wellness programs, and enhanced institutional support mechanisms. These steps were essential to upholding their professional commitment and avoiding burnout.

3. As it turned out, this study highlighted the immediate necessity of institutional reforms aimed at protecting the well-being of psychiatric nurses. An intervention of challenges by well-structured support programs enhanced job satisfaction, diminished burnout, and promoted a more resilient and motivated psychiatric nursing team, ultimately leading to increased quality of psychiatric care services offered in healthcare facilities.
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Recommendations

The study revealed the lived experience of weathered psychiatric nurses with long term exposure to psychiatric wards. The following suggestions were recommended in order to help psychiatric nurses, improve their workplace, and direct the construction of an Intervention Enhancement Program. These guidelines were addressed to psychiatric nurses, hospital administrators, mental health facilities, policymakers, government, and future researchers and researchers to improve workplace conditions and promote the wellbeing of psychiatric nurses.

1. **Psychiatric nurses.** Psychiatric nurses were encouraged to take an active role in personal resilience activities to cope with the emotional and psychological effect of their long-term exposure to psychiatric patients. Participation in peer support groups, debriefing, and professional counseling services provided an official channel for stress handling and emotional expression. Moreover, psychiatric nurses were also motivated to establish effective coping mechanisms, including work-life balance and mindfulness, in order to maintain their well-being. Institutions facilitated psychiatric nurses with continuous training in trauma-informed care, crisis management competencies, and psychological resilience to enhance their professional adaptability.
2. **Hospital Administrators.** Hospital administrators also moved proactively to develop an environment for work that reduced burnout and promoted job satisfaction. This involved optimizing nurse-to-patient ratios to avoid overwork, providing mental health support services, and designing formal wellness programs specifically targeting the unique experiences of psychiatric nurses. Administrators also developed a recognition culture where the value of the contributions of psychiatric nurses was respected through opportunities for career advancement, performance incentives, and long-term professional growth mentoring programs.
3. **Policymakers.** Policy makers implemented policies in the workplace that directly addressed the issues faced by psychiatric nurses. Legislation established minimum staffing ratios, fair assignment of workloads, and mental health care accessibility in psychiatric facilities. Governmental grants were also distributed to specialty psychiatric mental health programs that offered free counseling, wellness programs, and incentives for nurses to remain employed in psychiatric

environments longer. Support for higher wages, hazard pay, and mental health leave policies was raised to acknowledge the distinct requirements of psychiatric nursing.

4. **Government.** Government had a responsibility in the welfare of psychiatric nurses by making reforms in institutions and financing programs. Resilience training funded by the government, work safety monitoring, and wellness grants were created to support the long-term welfare of psychiatric nurses. Periodic checks of psychiatric institutions were also conducted by the government to check if institutions were complying with mental health and labor legislation in order to ensure psychiatric nurses got the care and protection they needed.
 5. **Future Researchers.** Future researchers continued exploring the long-term psychological impact of psychiatric nursing, particularly focusing on how prolonged exposure to psychiatric wards influenced their emotional well-being and job satisfaction. Studies examining the effectiveness of intervention programs, such as stress reduction techniques and support systems, provided valuable insights into improving psychiatric nurses' work environments. Future research also explored organizational strategies that enhanced psychiatric nurses' professional resilience and retention rates.
 6. As the lead researchers of this research, **the researchers**, headed by Ma. Angella Devine Alpha, Vince Edward Llega and Joemar Urrea, were committed to documenting the authentic lived experience of weathered psychiatric nurses and providing empirical evidence for future intervention programs. The research team suggested that academic institutions, hospital administrators, and mental health organizations join forces to create and implement focused strategies that emphasize psychiatric nurses' well-being. In addition, the incorporation of the study's results in nursing education curricula prepared future psychiatric nurses better to overcome the obstacles they may encounter within psychiatric environments.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research was carried out conserving the welfare of participants and their rights through this whole process, reviewed and approved by the Ethics Review Committee (ERC). The informed consent that was also approved by the ERC clearly explained the reason for the study, method for data collection, as well as possible risks and benefits involved. Some of the potential harm included emotional distress or discomfort that participants might feel when communicating their experiences during the interview. The participants were assured that they could withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences if they felt discomfort or became overwhelmed during the interview.

Several methods were employed to reduce distress. A debriefing question was also provided, just in case a sensitive issue surfaced during the interview, which then enables them to work through their emotions and leave knowing they've been heard and cared

for. Flexibility was then introduced in the interview in terms of stopping if participants feel uncomfortable or require more time to reflect on an experience. To avoid misunderstandings, the researchers explained the expectations during the interview process among the participants. The researchers conducted debriefing post-interview to ensure that the participant's well-being was well maintained.

Data confidentiality and privacy were maintained through tight controls for data storage and handling: all data collected, including voice recordings, was stored on an encrypted service, such as Google Drive, with secure login credentials and two-factor authentication. All identifiable information was de-identified or anonymized so that no individual participant's identity would be compromised. Republic Act 10173, otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, guides this research. The Act prescribes the collection, processing, and storage of personal data with respect to privacy, confidentiality, and security. As a precaution in relation to the Act, consent was sought and explicitly given by the participants prior to the collection of any data. The data will be used only for the purposes stated in the current study and dealt with and stored appropriately. Regular audits throughout the research process ensured that privacy protocols remained intact, and participants felt confident that their personal information was being handled responsibly.

The researchers maintain that this study was carried out with utmost concern for ethical research standards. The study did not pose any conflict of interest to carry out and all the ethics guidelines were considered to uphold the integrity of research. Informed consent was given in due regard, respondents' autonomy to withdraw was respected and anonymity was retained throughout the research. The researchers maintained fairness and impartiality in interpreting findings, refraining from any type of bias. Moreover, plagiarism was entirely refrained from, and all outcomes were utilized only for educational and research purposes. By these ethical standards, the study maintains the highest possible standards of research integrity, so that participants' rights, privacy, and well-being were ensured to remain intact at every stage.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to express their heartfelt gratitude to the following individuals and institutions that made this research possible.

Dr. Josephine Maningas, LPT, for the unyielding support, motivation, and belief in the importance of this study.

Ms. Christine Lae Erasga, RPsy, RPm, CHRA, to whom the researchers extended their gratitude for her support as the research adviser

Mr. Bernardo N. Fernandez II, MSP, RPm, CHRA, to whom heartfelt thanks were extended for the excellent mentorship throughout this study. The support laid a support foundation for successful completion of this research. The researchers were grateful for the undying support and encouragement.

Ms. Charie Jane Lao, JD, MSP, RPm, Ph.D. (CAR), CMHFR, CPFA, CMHA, CSFA, Ms. Psyche Reve Navarro, CMHFR, CHRA, MP, and Mr. Adrian Christian Pugate, RPsy,

RPm, CHRA, whose critical input and collaboration ensured that the study aids were trustworthy and authentic. Their expertise enormously contributed to our work, and the researchers immensely valued their efforts.

Level III Department of Health Hospital, the researchers acknowledged providing access to significant resources and data that supported this research. The Level III Department of Health Hospital efforts to increase mental health care was imperative in building the setting of this study.

Professional Education, Training, and Research Unit (PETRU), the researchers wished to convey their sincere gratitude for the critical assessment and meaningful comments that significantly enhanced the quality of this research. Their expertise ensured that the study met rigorous academic standards.

Ethics Review Committee (ERC), the researchers valued the tight monitoring that was afforded to ensure that the research was carried out according to the best ethical practices. Their commitment towards upholding participants' rights helped to steer the researchers through this sensitive phase.

Nursing Education and Training Service (NETS), the researchers appreciated their cooperation as well as their involvement. Nursing Education and Training Service (NETS) resources and support contributed to the success of this study.

Participants of the Study, to whom the researchers are greatly indebted, especially psychiatric nurses for their courage and willingness to share their valuable experiences. Their insights formed the basis of this research and revealed the truth surrounding psychiatric nursing practice. The researchers appreciated their openness and honesty, which provided a balanced image of the difficulties and successes in caring for patients. The study's significance and applicability were derived from their narrative sharing. The researchers recognized that the sharing of personal experiences requires a lot of courage, and researchers were very grateful to each participant for dedicating their time.

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